

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Some Mixed Ligand Bimetallic Tetrathiocyanato Complexes

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Bimetallic tetrathiocyanato complex having the formula $Ni(NCS)_2(PPh_3)_2Cu_2(SCN)_2$ has been synthesized and used as Lewis acid. It was reacted with a number of Lewis bases. The ligands become coordinated to nickel. The structures of these complexes are proposed on the basis of ir spectra, electronic spectra, conductance and magnetic moment values. The total softness values of Cu(I) and Ni(II) have also been evaluated and the difference used for establishing the nature of bonding in the complexes.

SEVERAL reports¹⁻⁴ have appeared on the studies of triphenylphosphine complexes with $MM'(NCS)_4$ [where $M=Co, Ni$; $M'=Hg^{++}, (Ag^+)_2, (Tl^+)_2$]. It was observed that when PPh_3 is linked with a metal, further linkage of the ligand to the metal is very difficult probably due to the large steric hindrance of the ligand.

This paper presents the studies of the complex of mixed ligand with a new type of bimetallic tetrathiocyanates $Ni(NCS)_2Cu_2(SCN)_2(PPh_3)_2$ as Lewis acid. PPh_3 is a common ligand in all the complexes whereas the other donors are of varying basicity.

Experimental

Materials and manipulations: All the solvents were purified before use. Reagent grade hydrated nickel(II) nitrate, hydrated copper(II) sulphate, potassium bisulphite and potassium thiocyanate were used as such from fresh bottles. Triphenylphosphine(PPh_3) was used after recrystallisation from acetone. Dioxan (diox), dimethylformamide (dmf), pyridine (py), aniline (anl) and bipyridine (bipy) (B.D.H.) were purified by known methods. Phenanthroline (phen), 3-aminopyridine (3-amp), 4-aminopyridine (4-amp), 2-aminopyrimidine (ampn), urea (ua), *p*-toluidine (tol), benzidine (ben), α -naphthylamine (nap) and nicotinamide (nia) were used after recrystallisation from alcohol. $Ni(NCS)_2$ and $CuSCN$ were prepared by known methods^{5,6}.

Syntheses of complexes: (i) $Cu(SCN)PPh_3$: 15 mmol solution of triphenylphosphine in acetone was added into a 15 mmol suspension of $CuSCN$ in the same solvent and stirred for 20 hr. Solid complexes formed was filtered, washed with the solvent and dried in vacuum.

(ii) $Ni(NCS)_2Cu_2(SCN)_2(PPh_3)_2$: 10 mmol of $Ni(NCS)_2$ and 20 mmol of $Cu(SCN)PPh_3$ were mixed together in ethyl acetate in a 250 ml flask and stirred for 48 hr. Greenish yellow complex,

formed at the end of the reaction was filtered, washed with ethyl acetate and dried in vacuum.

(iii) $(L)_nNi(NCS)_2Cu_2(SCN)_2(PPh_3)_2$; ($n=3$ when $L=bipy, phen, ben$; $n=0$ when $L=py, anl, nia, tol, nap, pip, 3-amp, 4-amp$ and $ampn$): Homogeneous suspensions of 2 mmol of $Ni(NCS)_2Cu_2(SCN)_2(PPh_3)_2$ in ethyl acetate were prepared in a number of 100 ml flasks. To these, solutions of different ligands were added in suitable molar ratio and stirred for 36 hr. Solid complexes formed were filtered, washed with the solvent and dried in vacuum.

(iv) $(L)_nNi(NCS)_2Cu_2(SCN)_2(PPh_3)_2$; ($n=2, L=dmf, ua$): 2 mmol of $Ni(NCS)_2$ and 4 mmol of $Cu(NCS)PPh_3$ were mixed together in ethyl acetate and stirred for 24 hr. The solution of the above ligands were added in suitable molar ratio and stirred for further 18 hr. Green complexes, formed at the end of the reaction, were filtered, washed with solvent and dried in vacuum.

Elemental analyses: Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoximate, copper as cuprous thiocyanate, sulphur as barium sulphate gravimetrically. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. The analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Physical measurements: The molar conductance of soluble complexes was measured in dimethylformamide with the Phillip PR-9500 conductivity bridge.

The infrared spectra in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded as nujol mull on Perkin-Elmer-621 model spectrophotometer. Far infrared spectra in the region 500-50 cm^{-1} were recorded on Polytech FIR-30 spectrophotometer as polyethylene pellets.

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 model spectrophotometer in the region 2500-250 nm.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Complexes	Colour	m.p. (°C)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%S		%Cu		%Ni		%N		M/512 (cm ⁻² mhos/mole)
				Calcd.	Obs.	Calcd.	Obs.	Calcd.	Obs.	Calcd.	Obs.	
Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	greenish yellow	212d	2.98	18.60	13.54	13.55	13.52	6.29	6.30	5.95	5.90	—
(dmf) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	green	145	3.02	11.73	11.62	11.55	11.50	5.41	5.43	7.69	7.61	—
(ua) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	green	203	3.11	12.07	12.01	11.87	11.76	5.09	5.06	10.56	10.50	70.9
[Ni(Py) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	light green	182d	3.10	9.04	9.06	8.90	8.32	4.17	4.13	9.89	9.86	104.5
[Ni(anl) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	light green	195d	3.06	8.54	8.50	8.41	8.32	3.94	3.96	9.84	9.39	—
[Ni(nia) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	yellow	190d	3.15	7.65	7.61	7.53	7.48	3.53	3.51	12.79	12.78	—
[Ni(pip) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	green	145	3.20	8.85	8.88	8.68	8.67	4.07	4.06	9.06	8.99	—
[Ni(tol) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	yellow	205	3.18	8.09	8.10	7.96	7.93	3.72	3.67	8.84	8.80	102.4
[Ni(nap) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	green	212	3.12	7.12	7.06	7.01	6.98	3.24	3.30	7.79	7.74	—
[Ni(3-amp) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	brown	205d	3.06	8.40	8.39	8.27	8.25	3.22	3.25	14.38	14.30	—
[Ni(4-amp) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	green	178d	3.08	8.40	8.33	8.27	8.32	3.26	3.20	14.38	14.36	111.2
[Ni(ampn) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	green	225d	3.15	8.47	8.45	8.34	8.35	3.90	3.75	20.37	20.32	—
[Ni(ben) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	green	215d	3.14	8.58	8.60	8.44	8.41	3.95	3.91	9.49	9.47	—
[Ni(bipy) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	grey	198	3.18	9.09	9.05	8.95	8.90	4.12	4.03	9.94	9.87	104.5
[Ni(phen) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	grey	208d	3.20	7.06	7.03	6.95	6.94	3.26	3.23	7.73	7.82	—

d=decomposes.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS (cm⁻¹)

Complexes	ν_2			10Dq	B'	β
	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$			
Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	25400	15930	9500	10110	750	0.73
(ua) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	27000	16940	10870	10760	780	0.76
[Ni(anl) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	26150	16250	10090	10230	785	0.78
[Ni(nia) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	27000	16660	10870	10480	830	0.80
[Ni(4-amp) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	26000	15930	10000	9160	770	0.75
[Ni(bipy) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	25640	16130	9960	10280	745	0.72

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by Gouy's method at room temperature using H₂Co(NCS)₄ as standard. Diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascals constant.

Results and Discussion

The studies of the complexes have been confined to electronic spectral, magnetic moment, infrared spectral and conductance measurements. Quantitative softness values of the metal ions and of the ligands were also evaluated and used to support the structures proposed on the basis of above studies.

Electronic spectral discussion : To extend support for the stereochemistry around nickel, we have recorded the electronic spectra of some representative complexes and the assignments are given in the Table 2. In all the complexes three bands due to transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) are observed. ν_3 is generally observed in the region 25000-27000 cm⁻¹, ν_2 in the region 15000-17000 cm⁻¹ and ν_1 in the region 9500-11000 cm⁻¹.

Dq, B' and β values were calculated using the matrices of Tanabe and Sugano⁷ from the values of ν_2 and ν_3 .

The position of electronic bands and the values of spectral parameters indicate an octahedral geometry around nickel. This geometry is also supported by magnetic moment values, which are included in Table 1.

Infrared spectral studies :

Lewis acid : (NCS)₂Ni(NCS)₂Cu₂(Ph₃P)₂ : Analytical data of the compound indicate that two molecules of Ph₃P are coordinated to each molecule of NiCu₂(SCN)₄. X-sensitive Wiffens bands of Ph₃P are shifted to higher frequencies which shows that the Ph₃P is coordinated to metal^{8,9}. The magnetic moment and electronic spectral data as discussed earlier indicate an octahedral geometry around nickel. On the basis of these results the following structures may be proposed.

The structure (c) appears to be more probable due to the following reasons :

- (i) The infrared spectral bands due to νCN , νCS and δNCS indicate the presence of only bridged thiocyanate groups¹⁰⁻¹³.
- (ii) Cu(I) prefers a linear structure instead of angular geometry^{8,14}. This also supports structure (c).
- (iii) The presence of bands in the region 220-225 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{Cu-P}$ mode¹⁵ and absence of bands due to $\nu\text{Ni-P}$ mode¹⁶ clearly support the structure (c).
- (iv) It has been previously observed that whenever Ph_3P is linked to nickel its coordination number does not exceed four and generally planar diamagnetic compounds of nickel are obtained¹⁸. Since our compound is paramagnetic this clearly rules out the linkage of Ph_3P to nickel.
- (v) The octahedral geometry is probably achieved by axial linking of S-end of the thiocyanate groups of other layer¹⁷.

Thiocyanate bridged complexes :

Analytical data show that two molecules of the ligands (dmf or ua) are coordinated to each molecule of $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$. Triphenylphosphine is coordinated similarly as in Lewis acid as indicated by the infrared spectral band positions. The electronic bands, spectral parameters and magnetic moment values suggest an octahedral environment around nickel. The far ir spectra show the presence of $\nu\text{Ni-NCS}$ bands.

On the basis of these results following structures can be postulated. The structure (e) appears to

Fig. 'd'

Fig. 'e'

Fig. 'f'

be most probable due to following reasons :

- (i) The position of ir spectral bands due to $\nu\text{C-N}$, $\nu\text{C-S}$ and δNCS modes indicate the presence of both bridged and terminal thiocyanate groups in these sets of complexes^{4,8}.
- (ii) It has been previously observed that whenever nickel is bonded to triphenylphosphine it does not exceed its coordination number beyond four¹⁸. This rules out structure (f).
- (iii) Cu(I) prefers linear structure instead of trigonal geometry^{8,14} as shown in Fig. e.
- (iv) $\nu\text{Ni-P}$ bands are generally observed in the region 148-190 cm^{-1} ¹⁶ whereas $\nu\text{Cu-P}$ stretching bands are assigned in the region 220-230 cm^{-1} ¹⁵ by Mores *et al* and in the region 180-230 cm^{-1} by Adams and co-workers¹⁸. In our complexes we observe bands in the region 220-225 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to $\nu\text{Cu-P}$ mode. The bands due to $\nu\text{Ni-P}$ mode are absent. This also favours validity of the structure (e).
- (v) 'dmf' shows features of coordination through their carbonyl oxygen as is evident by negative shift in $\nu\text{C=O}$ mode¹⁹. Carbonyl oxygen is donor site in urea also as is evidenced by negative shift in $\nu\text{C=O}$ mode. We observe bands due to $\nu\text{Ni-O}$ in the region 370-390 cm^{-1} .
- (vi) Octahedral geometry as required by magnetic moment values and electronic spectral studies are also satisfied.
- (vii) Linkage of S-end of thiocyanate to Cu(I) and nitrogen (-N) end to Ni(II) are in accordance with HSAB principle²⁰.

Cationic-Anionic complexes :

$[\text{NiL}_n][\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2$; (n=3, when L = bipy, phen and ben, n=6 when L = py, anl, nia, 3-amp, 4-amp, ampn, tol, nap, pip) : Analytical data indicate that six molecules of py, anl, nia, 3-amp, 4-amp, ampn, tol, nap and pip and three molecules of ben, bipy and phen are coordinated to one molecule of $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$. The ligands show feature of coordination as is evidenced by positive shifts in the bands of ring vibrations^{21,22}. Both the ring nitrogen of phen and bipy are involved in coordination. So they act as bidentate ligands. The nitrogen of NH_2 is the donor site in anl, tol, nap and ben as is evidenced by negative shift in $\nu\text{N-H}$ modes^{4,23}. The ir spectra show bands due to $\nu\text{C-N}$, $\nu\text{C-S}$ and δNCS modes in the region 2140-2080 cm^{-1} , 730-780 cm^{-1} and 430-455 cm^{-1} respectively. Bands in these regions are characteristic of S-bonded thiocyanate⁴. The electronic spectral bands, ligand field parameter and magnetic moment values show that the nickel is in octahedral geometry. Complexes formed by py, tol, 4-amp and bipy are soluble in dmf whereas rest are insoluble. Molar conductance of these complexes show

that they are 1 : 1 electrolyte. These complexes have similar magnetic moment values, spectral parameters and electronic bands.

On the basis of the preceding discussion it can be said that these complexes are cationic-anionic as described elsewhere^{1,2,3} and possible cation and anion are :

The following points also support the proposed structures :

- (i) The linkage of -S end of thiocyanate to Cu(I) is in accordance with HSAB principle.
- (ii) Presence of bands in the region 270-290 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu\text{Ni}-\text{L}$ mode^{2,2,2,4}.
- (iii) $\nu\text{Cu}-\text{P}$ bands are present in all the complexes.
- (iv) The $\Delta\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}-\text{Cu})$ values as discussed later also support the proposed structure.
- (v) Octahedral coordination around nickel as required by electronic spectral and magnetic moment values are also satisfied.

Quantitative softness values and structure of the complexes :

The proposed structures of complexes can also be supported by quantitative values of softness. The ligands on reaction with $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ have the choice of coordination either to Ni(II) or to Cu(I) as shown in Figs. x and y respectively.

In the preceding discussion structure (x) has been preferred. This is supported by calculating total softness difference values of nickel and copper^{2,5} by adopting following equations :

$$\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}) = E_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}) + 2E_m^{\dagger}(\text{L}) + 4E_m^{\dagger}(\text{NCS})$$

$$\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu}) = 2E_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu}) + 2E_m^{\dagger}(\text{SCN}) + 2E_m^{\dagger}(\text{PPh}_3)$$

$$\Delta\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}-\text{Cu}) = \text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}) - \text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu}) \quad \dots (1)$$

$\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni})$ and $\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu})$ are the total softness of the nickel and copper in complexes, respectively. $E_m^{\dagger}(-\text{NCS})$ and $E_m^{\dagger}(\text{SCN})$ are the softness of -N end and -S end of thiocyanates attached to nickel and copper respectively.

$$\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}) = E_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}) + 4E_m^{\dagger}(\text{NCS})$$

$$\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu}) = 2E_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu}) + 2E_m^{\dagger}(\text{L}) + E_m^{\dagger}(\text{SCN}) + 2E_m^{\dagger}(\text{PPh}_3)$$

$$\Delta\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}-\text{Cu}) = \text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}) - \text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Cu}) \quad \dots (2)$$

Similarly the total softness difference values for structure (y) has been calculated by using equation (2).

The structure, in which total softness difference value is higher, will be the most probable^{2,6}. The $\Delta\text{TE}_n^{\dagger}(\text{Ni}-\text{Cu})$ values are higher for structure (x) which shows that our proposed structure is correct.

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRAL BAND POSITIONS (cm^{-1})

Complexes	$\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$	$\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$	δNCS	$\nu\text{Ni}-\text{L}$	$\nu\text{Ni}-\text{NCS}$	$\nu\text{Cu}-\text{P}$
$\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$	2160s, 2095s	745s, 740s	450s	—	250w	220w
$(\text{dmf})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$	2160sh, 2095s	745s	450w	390m	240w	225w
$(\text{ua})_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$	2160m, 2120vs	745s, 775m	470w	370w	240m	223w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{py})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2120s, 2095s	752sh, 740s	480br	280sh	—	225m
$[\text{Ni}(\text{anl})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2115vs, 2080s	755s, 740s	480w	278sh	—	222w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{nia})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2140w, 2085s	780w, 740s	480w	280w	—	220w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{pip})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2180s, 2090sh	750m	480w	290sh	—	220w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tol})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2120s, 2095s	750sh, 740s	450w	290w	—	220w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{nap})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2120s, 2085s	760m, 740s	425br	290w	—	225w
$[\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-amp})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2130sh, 2095vs	785w, 745s	435w	278sh	—	225m
$[\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-amp})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2120sh, 2100vs	740s	485m	280w	—	220w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{ampn})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2140s, 2095s	745s, 760s	455s, 430m	280sh	—	220m
$[\text{Ni}(\text{ben})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2115vs, 2092s	740s, 735s	485w	292w	—	225w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2115sh, 2095s	760s, 740s	440w	275w	—	225w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_2]^{++}[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{PPh}_3)]_2^{-}$	2100s, 2090s	785w, 740s	480w	280m	—	225m

s=strong, vs=very strong, w=weak, m=medium, br=broad and sh=shoulder.

TABLE 4—SOFTNESS OF LIGANDS AND TOTAL SOFTNESS DIFFERENCE

Complexes	$E_m^\ddagger$ (ligand)	$\Delta TE_n^\ddagger$ (Ni—Cu) (structure x)	$\Delta TE_n^\ddagger$ (Ni—Cu) (structure y)
(dmf) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	-10.65	54.12	22.17
(ua) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Cu ₂ (SCN) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	-10.42	53.88	22.40
[Ni(py) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.75	17.68	8.92
[Ni(anl) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.54	16.42	7.66
[Ni(nia) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-18.90	30.58	21.82
[Ni(pip) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.89	15.52	6.76
[Ni(tol) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.38	15.46	6.70
[Ni(nap) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.41	15.64	6.88
[Ni(amp) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-12.02	19.30	10.54
[Ni(ampu) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.27	14.80	6.04
[Ni(bipy) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.70	17.88	8.62
[Ni(phen) ₂] ⁺⁺ [Cu(SCN) ₂ .PPh ₃] ₂ ⁻	-11.98	19.06	10.30

(i) The $E_m^\ddagger$ values of N(-NCS), S(-SCN) and PPh₃ have been taken as -12.65, -8.82 and -7.78 respectively.

(ii) The $E_n^\ddagger$ values of Ni(II) and Cu(I) have been taken as -0.82 and -2.65 respectively.

The $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger$ (Ni—Cu) values are also calculated for cationic-anionic complexes. These data as indicated in Table 4 show that PPh₃ is coordinated to Cu(I) and other ligands of the present series to Ni(II).

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